

MYTH AS ENVIRONMENTAL RESISTANCE TO ANTHROPOCENE IN AMITAV GHOSH'S JUNGLE NAMA: A STORY OF THE SUNDARBAN

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Abstract

*The researcher has aimed to analyse Amitav Ghosh's *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban* in the light of environmental resistance it faced from the Anthropocene. The capitalist's paradigm and colonial regime have been exposed in the expounded study; which uncovers these oppressive practices which have poised challenges to the ecology. Ghosh's re-telling the legend of Bon Bibi – Bengali origin, which focused the coexistence of the human-nature binary. Ghosh's reimagination of myth in a form of oral storytelling in *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban* as a living ethical framework which foster coexistence, nature-human harmony, and moral ethical responsibility toward the natural world.*

*This research paper expounds Ghosh's *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban*' use of myth: Bon Bibi a goddess who protects the forest as a form of environmental resistance; challenging modern human exceptionalism, capitalist extraction and colonial ecological agency. The inherent human greed for the advancement to claim the higher-rank in life; which human seek for material possessions even at the cost of the exploitations of the nature this has been exposed in the proposed study, and the rift between human-nature is apparent. However, eventually, the unification of human-nature binary is also evident in *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban*.*

The researcher has explored the above-mentioned thematic concerns especially with the consideration of the cause and effect of the capitalist extraction of the natural resources from the mangroves of the Sundarbans forests, thus exposed the complicated relationship of human with nature.

Keywords: Anthropocene, Resistance, Myth, Ecological Narrative, Capitalism, Ecocentrism

Amitav Ghosh is a renowned Indian-English writer and his art lies in the storytelling narrative techniques and his *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban* (2021) is not different in that sense, inspired from the legend of Bon Bibi from the Sundarbans (Bengali origin) and oral storytelling. Ghosh's *Jungle Nama* is a re-telling of the legend from the Sundarbans and it is

written in a poetic verse form, it revives the indigenous knowledge of oral storytelling as a means of articulating environmental ethics which primarily grounded in the harmony of nature-human binary, coexistence and ethical moral responsibility of human. This research paper examines Ghosh's *Jungle Nama* with the consideration of the myth as environmental resistance to Anthropocene poisoning challenges to the views of capitalist extractions and the dominant human hegemony. "In accounts of the history of the present climate crisis, capitalism is very often the pivot on which the narrative turns ..." (Ghosh, *The Great Derangement: Climate Change and the Unthinkable* 117) capitalism is indeed a pivotal in articulating environmental narratives. Through its narrative structure, poetic verse form and symbolic mythological characters, *Jungle Nama* demonstrates: indigenous myth with a powerful alternative environmental worldview in the contemporary age of climate crisis.

Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban have a limited number of characters, however, the capitalist venture of the forests of Sundarbans is well depicted by Ghosh. Dhona a character of the *story* who is a merchant and, on a venture, to commodify Sundarbans forests in order to be rich, this inhuman desire presented him as a true capitalist, his material quench to move higher in life has disharmonized the relationship of the mutual connection between nature and human. The *story* take place in the forests of the Sundarbans located in Bengal, which has considered as one of the largest mangroves forests in the world. Ghosh's use of rich ecological descriptions of the Sundarbans forests has created reminiscent of *The Hungry Tide* (2004) which has the Sundarbans at the core of the novel, and Ghosh's passion for ecological descriptions were well admired by the readers, same is the case with *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban*. The *story* has portrayed the continuous environmental resistance from the Anthropocene; especially from the capitalist Dhona; who quests in search of the natural resources of the Sundarbans forests. Ghosh has avoided labelling him as "colonist", however, from the inferences drawn from his character; substantially presents him as a colonist, if not the case with the label; his dehumanize actions perpetually served the purpose of the terminology.

Ghosh has inspired from the legend of Bon Bibi a Bengali origin, and he has re-told the myth of Bon Bibi and reframed the narrative in *Jungle Nama* which portrays the Bon Bibi a goddess of the mangroves of Sundarbans forests, who acts as a protector of nature and revitalises the environmental resistance, and throughout the *story* resisted to the Anthropocentric ventures of Dhona. The ecological commodification and its resistance are

centralizing themes of the *Jungle Nama*. Out of the blue, the normal conversation between the two brothers Dhona and Mona had inflamed the burning desire in Dhona to exploit the mangroves forests of the Sundarbans:

That spring Dhona was seized by an aching desire;
'I'll go to the mangroves, seven ships will I hire.
There's much to be had there, I'll take all I can see;
honey, wax and timber, and all of it for free!

(Ghosh, *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban* 10)

In the above-quoted citation in which the Dhona's desire to take everything from the nature and that too "for free" represents the true Anthropocentric spirit of Dhona. He had decided to begin his venture for the mangroves with "seven ships" – this embarkment clearly reveals his true intension; he was not going for the tour in one of the largest mangrove forests with the seven ships of labours but to exploit the invaluable riches of the Sundarbans for instance, woods, wax, honey, timber etc. this inhuman anthropogenic activity which has faced resistance from the nature itself, where Ghosh has brought the myth of Bon Bibi, a goddess who protects the mangroves of the Sundarbans through the magical divine power. Hence, the myth of Bon Bibi acts as a form of environmental resistance to Anthropocene in the *Jungle Nama*.

The descriptions of the precious riches of the mangroves in *Jungle Nama* are similar to the ecological descriptions of the Great Mountain and Valley's riches of the indigenous people's Valley in *The Living Mountain: A fable of Our Times* (2022) by Ghosh, for instance, "... its flowers produced exquisitely scented honey; and its fruit was delicious to eat ..." (Ghosh, *The Living Mountain: A Fable for Our Times* 10) in both the works of Ghosh, the environmental resistance is apparent. "Crucially, regardless of whether the environmental crisis can be traced back to anthropocentrism, it is beyond any doubt that human activities drive the global environmental crisis, including climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution." (Droz 26) Ghosh's *The Hungry Tide* accounts the environmental disruption caused by the anthropogenic activities in the Sundarbans; hence, it is not the coincidences in which the frequent talks about climate crisis occurred where human activities are at the centre.

"I think it's high time we took on a daring venture;/ we'll make a great fortune, our biggest ever." (Ghosh, *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban* 10) Dhona's desire for wealth made him indifferent towards nature and allows him to violate the ethical contract between

nature and human. On the one part of the *Story* the myth of Bon Bibi acts as a preserver of the nature and favoured the coexistence of nature-human binary, and simultaneously on the other hand, the inhuman actions of Dhona creates hindrance for the Sundarbans and forces nature to play a role to resist the anthropogenic activities, these not just only violate the nature-human binary but also led our nature to face the planetary crisis. Similarities can be drawn to Dhona and the various Western colonial periods which had undergone this evil pursuit: exploiting nature. Despite the fact that the nationality of Dhona is not mentioned in the text; by the inferences drawn from his conversations, he is without any doubt Indian. Ironically, Dhona's capitalist extraction of the mangroves of the Sundarbans has not mistaken him out of the sphere of the foreign colonial dominations which had taken place all over the globe with different multitudes; but in reality, supposed him with a true colonial spirit to take whatever can be taken for the material fulfilment.

Ghosh has portrayed a character from the myth of Bon Bibi: Dokkhin Rai, who mainly assumes the form of a tiger and sometimes of a "shape-shifter spirit". The arrival of Dhona in the mangroves of the Sundarbans had awaken Dokkhin Rai, who conversed with Dhona and demanded the life of a young boy from the ship named Dukhey, who is actually the son of Dhona's cousin, as an exchange in agreement to provide them natural riches of the Sundarbans, and Dhona did the same, he gave up his own cousin's son in exchange of the invaluable riches of the Sundarbans. However, before the agreement has been made, Ghosh has narrated the awakening of Dokkhin Rai after a long period of time which symbolises the long period of the Sundarbans without any anthropogenic hindrances and with peacefulness of nature without any sort of resistance. The venture of Dhona with seven ships symbolises the human greed for the advancement in life, and the false belief that nature is for us and we are the masters; this human-centred perception is core of Anthropocentrism and violets the Ecocentrism in which nature are at the centre of our life, this violation of eco-centric channel creates the room for the *myth* in which, Bon Bibi a goddess who advocates nature and resisted the humility and rejection for nature from the human agency.

The environmental resistance is also apparent with the anger of Dokkhin Rai, when Dhona came up with seven ships "... disproportionate number of boats." (Vescovi 109) to take control of the natural riches of the Sundarbans, Dokkhin Rai rants: "You've come here like dacoits, without asking my leave;/ you can't fool me, I know you've come to steal and thief. / Did you think you could rob me without my knowing?" (Ghosh, *Jungle Nama: A Story of the*

Sundarban 34) with this ranting of Dokkhin Rai, Ghosh has clearly alerted the colonial capitalists' regimes to think about the nature before advancing upon it. With this resentment of Ghosh, he has used multiple words: "dacoits", "rob", "steal", "thieve" which indicate to the one thing when something is not ours even though we want to take possession of it. Marxist thinker Antonio Gramsci's concept of Hegemony is by consent rather by force, unlike it, the *Jungle Nama* presents the Hegemony by force and power. Dokkhin Rai's remarks of "without my permission" how you dare to entre in Sundarbans, which symbolises humans must seek the coherence with nature and be grateful to mother nature, who protects every living and non-living entity, and it is there for the betterment of everyone, and it's our moral responsibility to respect our mother nature and utilize the coherent relationship with nature fostering the nature-human binary. In the *story*, the vexation of Dokkhin Rai towards Dhona and his counterparts are clearly a form of resistance from them, and the statements by Dokkhin Rai also imposing the authority of nature; nature observes everything so did Dokkhin Rai, one of the symbolic representation of nature, who warned everyone who began the pursuit of the extraction in the Sundarbans that there is no scope of escapism from nature and nature cannot be fooled by the human exceptionalism. Ghosh complicates the binary of animal-human conflict, Dokkhin Rai assumes as tiger and his killing of humans is not out of malice but necessity, demonstrating the broader ecological constraint caused by shrinking habitats and human encroachments.

The crew of the ship had been filled with an appetite "... When the men saw the wax there rose a great uproar." (Ghosh, *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban* 46) "wax" is an invaluable thing and act as a commodity; hence the commodification of ecology is illustrated vividly by Ghosh throughout *Jungle Nama*. One such instance rendered by Ghosh here:

...Those riches you got, how did they materialize?
 Your cargo of beeswax is a fabulous prize.
 But behind it all there's something inhuman,
 it seems some force has awoken your inner demon.

(Ghosh, *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban* 48)

These depictions exposed the inhuman anthropogenic possessions of Dhona, thus uncovering the colonial mask and highlighting the spirit of capitalism. "beeswax" is considered as a grand prize and the question raised by Ghosh in the first line of the above-cited quote; how the precious riches materialize? The association of natural resources with material thing is

indirectly exposing commodification of nature, thus strengthens the environmental resistance to Anthropocene. “force” which has awoken the “inner demon” in Dhona is nothing but the quench to be at the higher place in life with the material gains, and that was the reason which is why he has driven behind the mangroves forests of the Sundarbans to fulfil the capitalist demands with the capitalist extractions of the same. As Val Plumwood in *Environmental Culture: The Ecological Crisis of Reason* (2002) remarks, “... economic rationality of capitalism achieve its position of dominance, by maximising class of other beings that are available as ‘resources’ for exploitation without constraint ...” (Plumwood 100) the environmental disruptions caused by the Anthropocene in the Sundarbans have failed to give justice to nature and its elements thus violating the coherence among the internal elements of the mangrove forests which forms an important role in sustainment of the Sundarbans. “Other beings” as put by Plumwood in which the subject of “Other” has been debatable especially in the field of Postcolonial Studies since its origin as a literary theory.

To sum up, the myth of Bon Bibi has acted in serving the purpose of environmental governance as well as resisted to Anthropocene. In the *story*, Bon Bibi a goddess protects and governs the mangroves of the Sundarbans forests as well as saved the life of a young fellow, Dukhey, who had been put at stake by Dhona in exchange of the precious riches of the Sundarbans; protecting Dukhey, Bon Bibi has alarmed the capitalist and colonial regimes against the exploitation of nature. Thus, the myth fosters environmental wisdom capable of resisting current ecological amnesia. *Jungle Nama* emphasizes that the mangrove forests of the Sundarbans are governed by moral laws rather than authoritarian human domination. Unlike contemporary environmental discourse, which often treats nature as mere object to be regulated, *Jungle Nama* presents nature as a moral subject which is capable of judgment. Bon Bibi’s authority challenges anthropocentric assumptions and insists that survival depends on ethical and moral restraint. Ghosh’s use of myth also resists the presumption of colonial epistemologies that frame nature as wilderness to be conquered. By reviving the myth of Bon Bibi through re-telling it in *Jungle Nama* Ghosh challenges the lingering effects of colonial environmental management, which are constant to shape development policies in the region; as the Sundarbans had undergone different colonial regimes in the history. The *myth* acts as a preserver of ecological values marginalized by colonial modernity. *Jungle Nama* counters Anthropocene by acknowledging the non-human force and the ecological coherence of all natural elements. The subject of the struggles of nature in resisting the anthropogenic activities

of Dhona has also been touched, the *myth* acts in the favour of environment and resisted to Anthropocene, thus, uncovers the violation in nature-human binary.

Works Cited

- Droz, Layna. "Anthropocentrism as the scapegoat of the environmental crisis: a review." *ETHICS IN SCIENCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL POLITICS* 22 (2022): 25-49. Online.
- Ghosh, Amitav. *Jungle Nama: A Story of the Sundarban*. New Delhi: Fourth Estate, 2024. Print.
- . *The Great Derangement: Climate Change and the Unthinkable*. New Delhi: Penguin Books India, 2016. Print.
- . *The Living Mountain: A Fable for Our Times*. New Delhi: HarperCollins Publishers India, 2022. Print.
- Plumwood, Val. *Environmental Culture: The Ecological Crisis of Reason*. London: Routledge, 2002. Print.
- Vescovi, Alessandro. "Amitav Ghosh's *Jungle Nama* Writing Beyond the Novel." *Lingue e Linguaggi* (2024): 105-117. print.